
THE MOST IMPORTANT FACTORS THAT HELP IN MASTERING FOREIGN LANGUAGES PERFECTLY

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Abstract.

This article deals with the subject of foreign language teaching methodology, serves to achieve the goal of formation of professional skills among students. The article describes the theoretical knowledge of the importance and methodology of textbooks in teaching a foreign language.

Key words.

Methodology, foreign language learning, innovative technology, lesson goal.

It is well known that the 21st century is the period of scientific and technical development, learning world languages is an important tool for keeping up with the world, as well as receiving information and news about the world.

As international relations develop, humanity also strives to enrich the stock of knowledge, to see the world without being tied to its territory. In order to achieve these, learning foreign languages is considered as one of the important choices. To date, especially in our country, learning foreign languages has become a priority. In the teaching of foreign languages, modern information communications are widely used. In order to improve the modern pedagogical skills of teachers, various advanced methods of teaching are being developed.

In particular, full familiarity with the studied language is the main foundation of language learning, which requires hard work. Along with learning each language, one gets information about the life, culture, and customs of those countries.

Also, it has been determined by experts that learning a language is the best way to strengthen memory. Language learning sharpens not only memory, but also brain activity. Anyone who wants to learn a foreign language can learn it independently. For this, a person should set a specific goal and be psychologically ready to learn a language. That is, learning a language requires a little diligence, strong will and an organized schedule. In particular, it is worth mentioning that Cato Lomb was considered one of the first simultaneous translators in the world, despite his chemistry. He was able to speak 16 languages fluently and translated easily in 8 languages. In his bestseller named "How do I learn a language?", he presented simple and easy ways to learn foreign languages based on 10 rules. Some of them:

- regular practice with the language being studied;
- making a study plan;
- always write comments in the notebook;
- good imprinting in the memory;
- not to be limited by theory;
- getting used to correcting mistakes;
- causes self-confidence and the like.

For example, it is appropriate to form the study of a foreign language through the following principles.

- to know grammar - the functional functions of words and sentences
- having enough vocabulary
- development of speaking skills
- to be aware of phonetics, i.e. letters and their properties

The role of motivation (interest) and external environment is very important in mastering this language. First of all, the interest and desire of the language learner is important. The healthiness of the external environment increases motivation day by day. Of course, this environment should be rich with learners of this language. The important part of this is that the exchange of ideas between learners of the same language, the joint search for solutions to problems (related to the language), and also forms mutual competition. This, in turn, helps to expand the worldview and significantly increase the level of knowledge.

Even if you fill out a questionnaire to get a job in an organization or company, you will definitely be asked "What foreign languages do you know?". It is natural that your eyes fall on the question. Because nowadays, knowing other foreign languages besides one's mother tongue is becoming one of the important requirements of almost all fields.

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